

Sexual selection matters in genetic rescue, but productivity benefits fade over time: A multi-generation experiment to inform conservation

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Description of the data and file structure

Test of sex and, sexual selection background, of genetic rescuers on the fitness of an inbred population.

Null entries in the data sets were not included in that or any future generations.

Abbreviations

KSS - Krakow Super Strain, Outbred ancestral population.

C - Control treatment, Inbred populations that received no rescue.

F - Female rescue treatment, Inbred populations that received rescue by a female KSS.

M - Male rescue treatment, Inbred populations that received rescue by a male KSS.

Control - Control treatment, Inbred populations that received no rescue.

Mo - Monogamy rescue treatment, Inbred populations that received rescue by a monogamous beetle.

Po - Polyandry rescue treatment, Inbred populations that received rescue by a Polyandrous beetle.

Mo control - Control population of monogamous beetles in experimental setup conditions (Not included in the analysis).

Po control - Control population of polygamous beetles in experimental setup conditions (Not included in the analysis).

Files and variables

File: SEL-GR.csv

Description: Productivity data for experiment with genetic rescue by different sexual selection regimes

Variables

- ID: Identifying number
- Generation: Generation after rescue
- Productivity: Number of adult offspring produced
- Isoline: Inbred line Identification

- Treatment: Treatment applied

File: SS-GR.csv

Description: Productivity data for experiment with genetic rescue by different sexes

Variables

- ID: Identifying number
- Generation: Generation after rescue
- Productivity: Number of adult offspring produced
- Isoline: Inbred line Identification
- Treatment: Treatment applied

File: Stress-SEL-GR.csv

Description: Productivity data for experiment with genetic rescue by different sexual selection regimes in stressful conditions

Variables

- ID: Identifying number
- Generation: Generation after rescue
- Productivity: Number of adult offspring produced
- Isoline: Inbred line Identification
- Treatment: Treatment applied

File: Stress-SS-GR.csv

Description: Productivity data for experiment with genetic rescue by different sexes in stressful conditions

Variables

- ID: Identifying number
- Generation: Generation after rescue
- Productivity: Number of adult offspring produced
- Isoline: Inbred line Identification
- Treatment: Treatment applied

Code/software

Statistical analyses were carried out in R V4.4.1 (R Core Team, 2024) utilising R studio version 2024.04.2+764 (Posit team, 2024). Tidyverse (Wickham et al., 2019), stats (R Core Team, 2024), Rmisc (Hope, 2022) and googlesheets4 (Bryan, 2023) were used for data management and exploration. Plots were created using ggplot2 (Wickham, 2016). The distribution of data was checked using the shapiro.test function (R Core Team, 2024). Generalised Linear Mixed Models (GLMMs) were fitted to test for differences in productivity between the experimental treatments using glmmTMB (Brooks et al., 2017). Model fit was checked using DHARMA (Hartig, 2022). Model parameters were checked for collinearity using variance inflation factor (Vif) scores with the check_collinearity function from performance (Lüdecke et al., 2021). There were no issues with overdispersion or collinearity (VIF: <3 for all variables) in any models. R² was determined using the r.squaredGLMM function in MuMIn (Bartoń, 2024). Post-hoc pairwise Tukey tests were carried out using multcomp (Hothorn et al., 2008).

full_script - R script as one whole file.

SEL-GR LOAD - Load packages and data for sexual selection experiments

SEL-GR FIGURE - Create figure for sexual selection experiments

SEL-GR MODELS - Run models for sexual selection experiments

SS-GR LOAD - Load packages and data for sex experiments

SS-GR FIGURE - Create figure for sex experiments

SS-GR MODELS - Run models for sex experiments

Supplementary files

ReadMe.pdf - PDF version of the README

Figure 1 - Figure 1 from the manuscript

Figure 2 - Figure 2 from the manuscript

Figure 3 - Figure 3 from the manuscript

Figure 4 - Figure 4 from the manuscript